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Complexation of Chlorophenoxyacetic Acid Herbicides with Some Plant Metal Ions

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Manuscript received 28 October 1980, revised 2 May 1981,
accepted 15 July 1981

It has been observed in our previous investigation¹ that plant auxins, such as, indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), indole-3-propanoic acid (IPA), indole-3-butanoic acid (IBA) and naphthalene-1-acetic acid (NAA) form considerably stable complexes in solution with Mg(II), Al(III), Ca(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV), thereby supporting complexation as the possible mode of action of these plant growth regulators. Since herbicide action is also an important process occurring in plants, the complexes of some herbicides, such as, PAA, 2, 4-D and 2, 4, 5-T with Al(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zr(IV) and Th(IV) have been studied in solution potentiometrically using Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique²⁻⁴, as employed by Irving and Rossotti⁵. The protonation constant of the ligands and the stepwise formation constants of these metal complexes have been calculated to explore complexation as a possible mode of action of these herbicides⁶⁻⁸.

Experimental

Material: All chemicals were of A. R. grade. The ligands were obtained direct from Fluka AG, Buchs, Switzerland and were used after further purification. Dioxan was purified by standard method and solutions of ligands were prepared in 50% aq. (v/v) dioxan and carbonate free double distilled water. Other solutions were prepared in water and standardised by appropriate standard

methods. A Beckman pH-meter having glass and calomel-electrode assembly was employed to record the pH values.

Procedure: The following three mixtures: (a) 10 ml (0.01 M) nitric acid + 5 ml (1.0 M) potassium nitrate, (b) mixture (a) + 10 ml (0.01 M) ligand solution, and (c) mixture (b) + 2 ml (0.01 M) metal solution, were prepared for each system (total volume 50 ml) and titrated against standard carbonate free 0.1 M NaOH solution at constant ionic strength 0.1 M (KNO₃) and temperature (20°) in 50% aq. dioxan(v/v). A 70% aq. dioxan(v/v) medium was chosen to keep the Zr(IV) and Th(IV) complexes in solution. The ratio of metal and ligand concentration was maintained 1:5 in order to satisfy the highest coordination number of the metal. From the pH-titration curves, values of various parameters ($\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and pL) were calculated by Irving Rossotti's methods⁵.

Results

Proton-Ligand systems: Ligand titration curves and the proton-ligand formation curves of the ligands under investigation clearly indicated the liberation of one proton showing the equilibrium, $HL \rightleftharpoons H^+ + L^-$. From proton-ligand formation curves, the values of protonation constants (pK_a) were obtained directly by interpolating at half $\bar{n}_A$ values. The pK_a values of PAA, 2, 4-D and 2, 4, 5-T at 20° and 30° were found to be 4.58, 4.35, 4.20 and 4.32, 4.24, 4.08 respectively.

Metal-Ligand systems: Examination of the representative titration curves (Fig. 1) showed that

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves:

- A: Free acid (—●—●—●—);
 B: Free acid + 2,4-D (—Δ—Δ—Δ—);
 C: Cu(II)-2,4-D (—▷—▷—▷—);
 D: Al(III)-2,4-D (—□—□—□—);
 E: Zr(IV)-2,4-D (—○—○—○—).

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metal-titration curves for all ligands were well separated from the respective ligand-titration curves. In the case of divalent metal ions (1:5 metal-ligand ratio) two inflexion points were observed. The first occurred at ~2 ml of alkali added followed by another inflexion at ~3 ml of alkali. In the case of trivalent and tetravalent metal ions for the same molar ratio no other inflexions except the last one was well defined. It thus suggests that in systems at higher metal-ligand ratios two complexes ML and ML₂ are formed with divalent metal ions.

In the presence of Al(III) and Fe(III) ions, the titration curves using all the ligands were substantially displaced to lower pH regions. The single steep inflexion probably indicated the overlapping formation of protonated and normal 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 metal-ligand complexes. The titration curves for Zr(IV) and Th(IV) were not that much apart from the respective ligand curves as it was in the case of trivalent metal ions. But the conclusion remained unchanged and the single steep inflexion indicated the overlapping formation of protonated and normal 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 metal-ligand complexes. No attempt has been made to evaluate separate formation constants and so 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 constants are mixed constants for tri- and tetravalent metal ions indicating the total formation of the complex. At higher pH, precipitations occur and may be ascribed to hydrolytic effects. Thus, $\bar{n}$ calculations have been made before the precipitation of the complex solution. Formation curves for all the metal-ligand systems were complete at both the ends except for Zr(IV)-PAA, Zr(IV)-2,4-D, Th(IV)-PAA and Th(IV)-2,4-D systems which were incomplete in the lower half portions where the values of log K₂, log K₃ and log K₄ have been computed by 'correction term' and 'successive approximation methods' and values of log K₁ have been obtained from equation log K₁ K₂ = 2pL. Stepwise formation constants for Al(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes have been evaluated by interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values. 'Mid point' and 'correction term' methods have also been applied for Al(III) and Ni(II) complexes since K₁ and K₂ values are not far apart and the curves have been found to be symmetrical at the mid points. Formation curves for Fe(III) systems could not be obtained due to hydrolytic effects at very low pH values.

La(III) interacts with these acids at higher pH values (~7-8), but the $\bar{n}$ values have not been calculated because of hydrolysis in this pH range. So the successive constants could not be evaluated. Complexation could not be demonstrated with Mg(II) and Ca(II) ions. A comparison of the overall stability constant values (Table 1) shows that the general order of stability of these complexes with respect to metal ions is :

Th(IV) > Zr(IV) > Al(III) > Cu(II) > Co(II) > Ni(II), irrespective of the nature of the ligand involved. It has also been observed that the halogen substitutions and their position in the benzene ring of

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT DATA OF THE COMPLEXES OF PAA, 2,4-D AND 2,4,5-T WITH SOME METAL IONS OF BIOLOGICAL INTEREST (T=20°, $\mu=0.1 M KNO_3$)

Metal Complexes	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log K ₄	log β
<i>PAA-Complexes :</i>					
Al(III)	3.52	3.95	2.90	—	9.77
Co(II)	2.97	2.65	—	—	5.62
Ni(II)	2.50	1.75	—	—	4.25
Cu(II)	3.20	2.78	—	—	5.98
Zr(IV)	3.70	2.90	2.70	2.48	11.78
Th(IV)	3.75	3.65	3.35	3.25	14.00
<i>2,4-D-Complexes :</i>					
Al(III)	3.15	3.05	3.00	—	9.20
Co(II)	2.75	2.33	—	—	5.08
Ni(II)	2.20	2.00	—	—	4.20
Cu(II)	2.40	2.20	—	—	4.60
Zr(IV)	3.34	2.70	2.55	2.40	10.99
Th(IV)	3.59	2.85	2.50	2.10	11.04
<i>2,4,5-T-Complexes :</i>					
Al(III)	3.55	3.00	2.60	—	9.25
Co(II)	2.50	2.40	—	—	4.90
Ni(II)	2.05	1.90	—	—	3.95
Cu(II)	2.35	2.05	—	—	4.40
Zr(IV)	2.77	2.61	2.56	2.36	10.30
Th(IV)	3.05	2.50	2.22	1.72	9.49

phenoxyacetic acids have little but an important role in lowering their protonation and overall stability constants of metal complexes.

Discussion

It is evident from Table 1, that there is no significant difference in the chelating ability between the biologically active (2,4-D and 2,4,5-T) and inactive (PAA) herbicides. This indicates a somewhat similar electronic environment at the oxygen atoms involved in the complexation, irrespective of the ligand. On the other hand, halogen substitutions and their position in the benzene ring of phenoxyacetic acid have little but an important role in lowering the protonation constants and the overall stability constant values (Table 1) of metal complexes. The contribution of some other smaller or second order effects, such as, simple dissymmetry caused by any one sided substitution, the resonance interaction of chloro-groups, etc., which may influence the stability of these complexes may not be completely ruled out. The order of the stability constant values of these herbicides with metal ions was found to be PAA > 2,4-D > 2,4,5-T. A linear correlation between the overall stability constant values (log β) of these metal complexes with dissociation constant (pKa) of phenoxyacetic acids has been observed.

Our attempt to find a quantitative relationship between the mode of action of phenoxyacetic acid herbicides and the stability of their complexes with several metal ions of biological interest has yielded the conclusion that overall stability constants of biologically active (2,4-D and 2,4,5-T) and inactive (PAA) herbicides are almost similar. This indicates that chelation may not be the mode of

action of these herbicides. Further work to explore this hypothesis is in progress.

Acknowledgement

The financial support of this work from ICAR, New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are grateful to Dr. J. B. Singh (G. S. V. M. Medical College, Kanpur) for providing some experimental facilities.

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Potentiometric Determination of Stability Constants of Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III) Complexes with 5-Hydroxy-2-Methyl-1, 4-Naphthaquinone

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Manuscript received 13 October 1980, revised 18 June 1981,
accepted 15 July 1981

A survey of literature^{1,2} shows that no systematic study has been made on the chelating ability of 5-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone, commonly known as plumbagin. We reported³ recently the interaction of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with plumbagin in solution. In the present study, the stability constants of the metal chelates of plumbagin with Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III) are determined in 75% v/v ethanol-water mixture at 35° and 0.1 ionic strength.

Experimental

Plumbagin was isolated from the roots of the plant *Plumbago zeylanica*, following the method of Roy *et al.*⁴. The purity of the compound was checked by tlc and melting point. Standard solution of plumbagin was prepared in double distilled ethanol. All other chemicals were of AR grade. The rare earth metal nitrates were obtained from Indian Rare Earths Limited, Udyogamandal. The

metal contents of the solutions were determined by complexometric titrations with EDTA⁵.

An ELICO digital pH meter model LI-120, fitted with a combined electrode type CN-67, capable of reading ± 0.01 was used for pH measurements. The pH values were corrected in aquo-organic mixtures using the method of Van-Uitert and Hass⁶.

The experimental part consists of titration of the following solutions (total volume 50 ml), thermostated at $35^\circ \pm 0.01$ against carbon dioxide free NaOH ($5 \times 10^{-2} M$):

Plumbagin was taken four times in excess of the metal ion to avoid possible hydrolysis of metal ions.

Results and Discussion

The pH titration technique of Irving-Rossotti⁷ was used to obtain the values of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and pL from the pH titration curves. The pK_a value of plumbagin obtained from the plot of $\log \left(\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right)$ vs pH was found to be 9.93 ± 0.02 . The maximum value of $\bar{n}$ obtained in the pH region where hydrolysis of metal ion was negligible, was between 1.5 and 2.0 for Pr(III) and Nd(III) whereas it was between 2 and 3 for Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III). This indicates the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes in general and also 1:3 complexes in case of Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III). The metal-ligand stability constants were computed by means of simultaneous equations as described by Block and McIntyre⁸. The least squares method and the correction term method⁹ were also used to evaluate the formation constants in case of Pr(III) and Nd(III). The refined log K values are stated in Table 1.

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE CHELATES OF Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) AND Dy(III) WITH PLUMBAGIN IN 75% v/v ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE AT 35° AND 0.1 IONIC STRENGTH

Metal Ion	log K_1	log K_2	log K_3
Pr(III)	6.65	6.36	—
Nd(III)	6.70	6.51	—
Sm(III)	6.97	6.70	6.49
Gd(III)	7.05	6.72	6.51
Dy(III)	7.31	7.12	6.54

The log K values follow the order Pr(III) < Nd(III) < Sm(III) < Gd(III) < Dy(III). The increase in stabilities of rare earth metal complexes with decrease in ionic or crystal radii indicates the absence of extensive covalent bonding due to non-availability of 4f electrons for bond formation. The near linear plot of Z^2/r vs $\log \beta_2$ of these complexes is in accordance with the Born equation